

EFFECT OF BIO-SLURRY ON TOMATO PRODUCTION IN FLOODPLAIN SOIL

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted at the Soil Science Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, in order to evaluate the performance of bio-slurry on the production of tomato on floodplain soil. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 3 replications and comprised of six treatments viz., T₀ - Control, T₁ - Recommended fertilizer Dose (RFD), T₂ - 60% RFD + Poultry Manure (PM), T₃ - 60% RFD + Poultry slurry, T₄ - 60% RFD + Cow-dung (CD), T₅ - 60% RFD + Cow-dung slurry. The growth and yield of tomato were significantly influenced by the application of different manure. The tallest (61.10cm) plant was observed in T₂ (Poultry Manure) while the shortest plant (25.17cm) was found in T₀ (control). The highest number of fruits plant⁻¹ (27.87) was produced in T₁ (RFD) and it was lowest (9.77) in T₀ (Control). The highest average fruit weight (50.00 g fruit⁻¹) was observed in T₂ (Poultry Manure) and the lowest (26.00 g fruit⁻¹) was in T₀ (control). The highest yield (27.20 t ha⁻¹) was recorded in T₃ (60% RFD+ Poultry slurry) followed by T₁ (18.87 t ha⁻¹), T₂ (16.13 t ha⁻¹), T₄ (16.03 t ha⁻¹), T₅ (15.15 t ha⁻¹) and the lowest (8.35 t ha⁻¹) in control T₀ (control). The yield of tomato were increased by 126, 93, 225, 92 and 81% over control in T₁ (100% RFD), T₂ (60% RFD+ Poultry manure), T₃ (60% RFD+ Poultry slurry), T₄ (60% RFD+ Cow-dung), and T₅ (60% RFD+ Cow-dung slurry), respectively.

Key words: Bio-slurry, growth, yield, tomato

INTRODUCTION

Soil fertility is in declining trend in Bangladesh, which is mainly because of increasing cropping intensity and use of HYVs coupled with the minimum use of organic manure. According to an appraisal report of Bangladesh soil resources, soils of about 6.10 m ha contain very low (less than 1%) organic matter, 2.15 m ha contain low (1-2%) organic matter and the remaining 0.90 m ha contain more than 2% organic matter (Mondal, 2000). A good soil should have an organic matter content of at least 2.5% (BARC, 2005). But in Bangladesh, most soils have less than 1.7%, and some soils have even less than 1% organic matter. The average organic matter content of top soils has declined by 20-46% over past 20 years due to intensive cropping without inclusion of legume crops, imbalance use of fertilizer, use of modern varieties and scanty use of organic manure. It is agreed that decreases in soil fertility is a major constraint for higher crop production in Bangladesh.

The beneficial effect of organic manure in crop production has been demonstrated by many workers (Joshi *et al.*, 1994; Batsai *et al.*, 1979; Singh *et al.*, 1970 and Subhan, 1991). Maintenance of soil fertility is a prerequisite for long term sustainable crop production and it is certain that organic manure (cow-dung, poultry manure and their slurry) can play a vital role in the sustainability of soil fertility and crop production. So, the maintenance of soil organic matter is a burning issue both for the farmers and agricultural scientists. Application of by-product of the recently popularized biogas technology named 'bio-slurry' in soil could be one of the options to maintain declining soil fertility of Bangladesh.

Bio-slurry can improve the physical and biological quality of soil by adding organic matter to the soil. It also provides both macro and micro-nutrients to crops. These improve in water holding capacity, cation exchange capacity, lesser soil erosion and provision of nutrients to plants and soil micro-flora including N fixing and P solubilizing organisms. Apart from the nutrient supply, bio-slurry can inhibit pest attack e.g. nematode attack

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on tomato also can inhibit weed seed germination. The fermentation process reduces C/N ratio by removing some of the carbon thus increases nutrient concentration. Preliminary investigations showed that both cow-dung and poultry litter slurry contains considerable quantities of plant nutrients, which may be used to improve soil fertility and thus the use of chemical fertilizers can be reduced to a great extent.

Research works on the quality of bio-slurry and its effect on performance of crops grown in different soils and environment is lacking in Bangladesh. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the quality of bio-slurry and its effect on performance of different crops particularly vegetables where manuring is better for its quality than chemical fertilization. Under such circumstances, this piece of research work was conducted to study the nutrient concentration in different manure and bio-slurry and to observe the effect of different manure and bio-slurry on tomato production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site and planting material

The experiment was conducted at the Soil Science field Lab of Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, during the period from November 2011 to April 2012. The site was belonged to the Non calcareous Dark Grey Floodplain Soils under the Agro-Ecological Zone (AEZ-9) of Old Brahmaputra Floodplain (FAO and UNDP, 1988). In this experiment a tomato variety, Ruma VF, was used as experimental material. This mutant is usually cultivated as a winter variety, which is high yielding and disease resistant. It requires 60 to 65 days to mature.

Collection of soil samples

The initial soil sample was collected from Soil Science Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh.

Chemical analysis of soil samples

Soil pH was determined as described by Jackson (1973). Organic carbon was determined as outlined by Page *et al.* (1982) and the organic matter was calculated by following Van Bemmelen factor of 1.73. Total N was determined as described by Bremner and Mulvaney (1982) while available P was extracted following Olsen *et al.* (1954). Exchangeable K was determined as described by Thomas (1982) and available S content by Williams and Steinberg (1952).

Collection of manure and slurry

Poultry manure and poultry slurry were collected from Krishibid Poultry Farm, Valuka, Mymensingh. Cow-dung and cow-dung slurry were collected from dairy farm of Bangladesh Agricultural University.

Chemical analysis of manure and slurry

Manure and slurry Samples were analyzed for determination of N, P, K and S concentrations and were determined following the same method as used in soil chemical analysis.

Experimental protocol

The experiment comprised of six treatments *viz.*, T₀ - Control, T₁ - Recommended fertilizer Dose (RFD), T₂ - 60% RFD + Poultry Manure (PM), T₃ - 60% RFD + Poultry slurry, T₄ - 60% RFD + Cow-dung (CD), T₅ - 60% RFD + Cow-dung slurry. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 3 replications. There were 18 plots (6×3) and the area of each plot was 4m × 2.5 m. After final land preparation the experimental plot was fertilized as per recommendation of BARI (2005). Healthy and uniform sized 30 days old seedlings were transplanted in the experimental plots in the afternoon on 17 November 2011. After transplanting remaining seedlings were kept aside for gap filling. Intercultural operations were performed as and when necessary throughout the growth period of the crop according to the recommendation of BARRI (2008). Fruits were harvested at full maturity. Harvesting was done at several times. Time duration of harvesting was 12 February to 26 April 2012.

Data collection

The plant height (cm) was recorded at 56 DAT and measured from the ground level to the tip of the longest stem and mean value of 10 plants was calculated. Total number of fruits plant⁻¹ was calculated by taking mean value of 10 plants per plot. The fruit weight (g) was calculated by taking mean value of ten fruits per plot. Finally the yield was calculated in kg plot⁻¹ and then it was converted into t ha⁻¹.

Statistical analysis

The recorded data were compiled and statistically analyzed for ANOVA with the computer package MSTAT-C (Russell, 1986). A one way ANOVA was made by F variance test. The pair comparisons were performed by Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at 1% level of probability (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of nutrient content in manures and slurry

Organic matter

The organic matter (OM) content of different manures and bio-slurry was significantly different at 1% level of probability and varied from 32.0% to 69.5% (dry basis) (Table 1). The highest OM content (69.5%) was observed in cow-dung and the lowest (32.0%) was found in poultry manure while in soil it was 3.13%. The OM content of cow-dung slurry and poultry slurry was 43.5% and 32.4%, respectively. The results were relevant with the findings of ATC (1997) who found 41.46% OM content in sun-dried bio-slurry.

But in the wet basis (at 40% moisture content), the OM content was varied from 22.9% to 49.7% among the treatments (Table 1).

Nitrogen (N)

The N content of different manures and bio-slurry was significantly different at 1% level of probability and varied from 1.51% to 2.94% among the treatments (dry basis) (Table 1). The highest value (2.94%) was observed in poultry manure and the lowest (1.51%) was found in cow-dung slurry while in soil it was 0.05%. The N content of poultry slurry and cow-dung was statistically similar. Again nitrogen content was recorded from 1.08% to 2.10% among the treatments on wet basis (Table 1). Nitrogen content of cow-dung, cow-dung slurry, poultry manure, and poultry slurry was 1.44%, 1.08%, 2.10% and 1.52%, respectively on wet basis. This result was in the range of previously reported N content of 1.5-2.0% in fresh cow-dung slurry by Tripathi (1993) and Acharya, (1961). In all cases N contents of cow-dung and poultry bio-slurry were always found lower than those of the raw cow-dung and poultry manure. It could be due to the fact that the water soluble N in bio-slurry as ammoniacal form accounting 12-18% of total N (Acharya, 1961) was lost through volatilisation during the evaporation and drying of the digested paste like slurry due to alkaline pH of the slurry (Acharya, 1961; Chawla, 1984).

Phosphorus (P)

The P content of different manures and bio-slurry was significantly different at 1% level of significance. P content was varied from 0.51% to 0.81% (dry basis) (Table 1). The highest (0.81%) was observed in cow-dung while the lowest (0.51%) was found in cow-dung slurry and in soil P was found 0.0011%. In the wet basis P content was varied from 0.37% to 0.58% among the treatments (Table 1). The highest 0.58% was observed in cow-dung and the lowest 0.37% was found in cow-dung slurry. The phosphorus content of poultry manure and poultry slurry on wet basis was 0.51% and 0.56%, respectively. This findings are in agreement with Demont *et al.* (1991).

Potassium (K)

The K content was varied from 0.45% to 1.36% among slurry and manure (dry basis) (Table 1). The highest K content (1.36%) was observed in poultry manure and the lowest (0.45%) was found in cow-dung slurry. The K content in manures followed the trends: poultry manure > cow-dung > poultry slurry > cow-dung slurry. In all cases K content of cow-dung and poultry bio-slurry was always found lower than the corresponding value of

the raw cow-dung and poultry manure. It could be due to the fact that the water soluble K in bio-slurry was lost through leaching during the drying of the digested paste like slurry in a soil pit. K content in soil was about 0.002%. Again K content was recorded between 0.32% and 0.97% on wet basis (Table 1) while cow-dung, cow-dung slurry, poultry manure, and poultry slurry contain 0.82%, 0.32%, 0.97% and 0.75% K, respectively. These results are in the range of K content of 0.6-1.5% reported by Demont *et al.* (1991), Tripathi (1993) and Gupta (1991).

Sulphur (S)

There was no significant difference in sulphur (S) content among the different manures and bio-slurry. S content was varied from 0.39% to 0.46% among the treatments (dry basis) (Table 1). The highest S (0.46%) was observed in poultry slurry while the lowest (0.39%) was found in cow-dung. In soil, the value was 0.0012%. In the wet basis S content was varied from 0.33% to 0.28% among the treatments (Table 1). The S content of poultry manure and cow-dung slurry was similar and it was 0.31%.

Table 1: Nutrient content of cow-dung, cow-dung slurry, poultry manure, poultry slurry and soil

Particulars	%OM	%N	%P	%K	%S	Remarks
Cow-dung	69.5±0.20a	2.02±0.22b	0.81±0.01a	1.15±0.00b	0.39±0.04	Dry basis
	49.7±1.27a	1.44±0.23b	0.58±0.01a	0.82±0.00b	0.28±0.04	Wet basis
Cow-dung Slurry	43.5±0.50b	1.51±0.06c	0.51±0.09b	0.45±0.00d	0.43±0.09	Dry basis
	31.1±1.01b	1.08±0.06c	0.37±0.09b	0.32±0.00d	0.31±0.09	Wet basis
Poultry Manure	32.0±1.00c	2.94±0.20a	0.71±0.01a	1.36±0.01a	0.43±0.04	Dry basis
	22.9±0.25c	2.10±0.2a	0.51±0.01a	0.97±0.01a	0.31±0.04	Wet basis
Poultry Slurry	32.4±0.38c	2.13±0.06b	0.79±0.07a	1.05±0.00c	0.46±0.03	Dry basis
	23.1±0.12c	1.52±0.07b	0.56±0.07a	0.75±0.00c	0.33±0.03	Wet basis
Soil	3.13±0.18	0.05	0.0011	0.002	0.0012	
SE±	4.60	0.16	0.04	0.10	0.02	
LSD	0.65	0.168	0.069	0.015	-	
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	NS	

In a column, means followed by same letter(s) do not differ significantly at 5% level by DMRT; *Significant at 5% level of probability, ** Significant at 1% level of probability; NS = Non Significant, SE (±) = standard error of means, RFD = Recommended Fertilizer Dose

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Plant height

The effect of different treatments on plant height was statistically significant at 1% level of probability (Table 2). Plant height was varied from 25.17cm to 61.10cm among the treatments. The tallest (61.10cm) plant was observed in T₂ (60% RFD+ poultry manure) while the shortest plant (25.17cm) was found in T₀ (control). The plant height recorded in T₁ (100% RFD) and T₃ (60% RFD+ poultry slurry) was statically similar and superior to T₄ (60% RFD+ cow-dung) and T₅ (60% RFD+ cow-dung slurry). The plant height obtained from different treatments ranked in the order of T₂ > T₃ > T₁ > T₄ > T₅ > T₀. The reasons of obtaining tallest plant in T₂ might be due to the higher percentage of N, P, K and S in poultry manure. The percentages of increased plant height over control due to different treatments were presented in Table 3. The highest percentage (142.75%) of increased plant height over control was recorded in the treatment T₂ (60% RFD + poultry manure). The lowest percentage (80.89%) of increased plant height over control was recorded in the treatment T₅ (60% RFD + cow-dung slurry).

Table 2: Effect of manure and bio-slurry on yield and yield contributing characters of tomato

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	No. of fruits per plant	Wt. of fruits (g)	Yield (t/ha)
T ₀ (Control)	25.17d	9.77b	26.00c	8.35c
T ₁ (100% RFD)	53.80b	27.87a	38.33abc	18.87b
T ₂ (60% RFD + poultry manure)	61.10a	25.27a	50.00a	16.13b
T ₃ (60% RFD + poultry slurry)	56.80b	26.50a	48.33a	27.20a
T ₄ (60% RFD + cow-dung)	47.43c	21.23a	33.33bc	16.03b
T ₅ (60% RFD + cow-dung slurry)	45.53c	21.33a	41.67ab	15.15c
SE±	2.84	1.65	2.44	1.46
LSD	1.80	4.04	7.10	2.77
Level of significant	**	**	**	**

In a column, means followed by same letter(s) do not differ significantly at 5% level by DMRT; *Significant at 5% level of probability, ** Significant at 1% level of probability; NS = Non Significant, SE (±) = standard error of means, RFD = Recommended Fertilizer Dose

Table 3: The percentages of increased values of different parameters over control (T₀)

Treatments	Plant height	No. of fruits per plant	Wt. of fruits	Yield
T ₁ (100% RFD)	113.74	185.26	47.42	126.00
T ₂ (60% RFD + poultry manure)	142.75	158.64	92.30	93.00
T ₃ (60% RFD + poultry slurry)	125.66	171.24	85.88	225.00
T ₄ (60% RFD + cow-dung)	88.43	117.30	28.19	92.00
T ₅ (60% RFD + cow-dung slurry)	80.89	118.32	60.27	81.00

Number of fruits plant⁻¹

The number of fruits plant⁻¹ was significantly influenced by different manure and slurry treatments (Table 2). The highest number of fruits plant⁻¹ (27.87) was produced in T₁ (100% RFD) treatment and it was lowest (9.77) in T₀ (Control) treatment. Overall results of number of fruits plant⁻¹ indicated that the highest number of fruits plant⁻¹ was in T₁ treatment (27.87) followed by the treatment T₃ (26.50), T₂ (25.27), T₅ (21.33), T₄ (21.23), T₀ (9.77). The number of fruits plant⁻¹ was statistically similar in all the treatment except control. The percentages of increased number of fruits plant⁻¹ over control due to different treatments were also presented in the Table 3. The highest percentage (185.26%) of increased number of fruits plant⁻¹ over control was recorded in the treatment T₁ (100% RFD). The lowest percentage (117.30%) of increased number of fruits plant⁻¹ over control was recorded in the treatment T₄ (60% RFD+ cow-dung). The results indicate that the application of full recommended doses of chemical fertilizer (T₁) had the best effect on the number of fruits plant⁻¹ of tomato.

Fruit weight

The data on the average fruit weight of tomato was analyzed and shown in Table 2. The fruit weight of tomato was significantly influenced by different manure and slurry treatments. From the result it was observed that the average highest fruit weight was recorded in T₂ treatment (50.00 g fruit⁻¹) followed by T₃ (48.33 g fruit⁻¹), T₅ (41.67 g fruit⁻¹), T₁ (38.33 g fruit⁻¹), T₄ (33.33 g fruit⁻¹) and the lowest in T₀ (26.00 g fruit⁻¹) treatment. The fruit weight of tomato was statistically similar in T₁, T₂, T₅ and T₄. The percentages of fruit weight increased over control due to different treatments were presented in the Table 3. The highest percentage (92.30%) of increased fruit weight over control was recorded in the treatment T₂ (60% RFD+ poultry manure). The lowest percentage (28.19%) of increased fruit weight over control was recorded in the treatment T₄ (60% RFD+ cow-dung). The results indicated that the application of poultry manure (T₂) had the best effect on the average fruit weight of tomato.

Yield

The yield of tomato was significantly influenced by the application of different slurry and manure and chemical fertilizers. The yield of tomato varied from 8.35 to 27.20 t/ha in different treatments combinations. The highest yield (27.20 t/ha) was recorded in T₃ (60% RFD + poultry slurry) treatment and the lowest yield (8.35 t ha⁻¹) was observed in control (T₀) treatment (Table 2). Overall results of yield indicated that the highest yield was in T₃ treatment (27.20 t ha⁻¹) followed by the treatment T₁ (18.87 t ha⁻¹), T₂ (16.13 t ha⁻¹), T₄ (16.03 t ha⁻¹), T₅ (15.15 t ha⁻¹), T₀ (8.35 t ha⁻¹). The yield of tomato was statistically similar in T₁ (100% RFD), T₂ (60% RFD+ poultry manure) and T₄ (60% RFD + cow-dung) treatments. The percentages of yield increased over control due to different treatments were presented in the Table 3. The yield of tomato were increased by 126, 93, 225, 92 and 81 % over control in T₁ (100% RFD), T₂ (60% RFD + poultry manure), T₃ (60% RFD + poultry slurry), T₄ (60% RFD + cow-dung), and T₅ (60% RFD + cow-dung slurry), respectively. The results indicated that the application of poultry bio-slurry (T₃) had the best effect on yield of tomato.

The above stated results are in line with the finding of Maskey (1978) who reported that all crops including tomato gave higher yield with bio-slurry. There was yield increase of 19% in tomato due to application of bio-slurry compared with the untreated one. In another study, Renuka and Sankar (2001) concluded that vigorous growth of tomato with early flowering and high yield (46.66 tons) could be obtained with the application of FYM + bio-slurry, recording an increased yield of two and half times over the control (18.44 tons). Moreover, Sen *et al.* (2007) found that application of cow-dung (CD) or cow-dung slurry @10 t ha⁻¹ provided moderate yield (77.5 t ha⁻¹) of tomato. Application of bio-slurry 5 t ha⁻¹ along with 75% recommended dose of chemical fertilizer out yielded the full dose of recommended chemical fertilizer. They also reported that poultry slurry showed the best performance among the 4 organic manures in cabbage production and soil health followed by poultry manure, cow-dung slurry and cow-dung (Sen *et al.*, 2007). Better performance of poultry manure slurry and poultry manure compared to the cow-dung and cow-dung slurry as well as chemical fertilizer might be due to the fact that poultry manure content a large amount of uric acid. This uric acid constitutes 60 per cent of the nitrogen in poultry manures that changes rapidly to ammoniacal form which is utilized by the plants. Another important factor contributing to the higher yield with poultry manure might be their higher N content or increased availability of native soil nitrogen through increased biological activity (Smith, 1950). Furthermore, application of organic manures maintained the soil pH near to neutral, besides keeping lower levels of electrical conductivity and bulk density (Renuka and Sankar, 2001).

Most studies have thus reported some combination of biogas slurry with chemical fertilizer to be more effective over FYM and chemical fertilizer. A survey of farmers opinions and perception about the use of biogas slurry in a village in Uttar Pradesh reported the following finding: "With HYV seeds, productivity is in the order: slurry + chemical fertilizer > Heap Manure + Chemical fertilizer (Santosh *et al.*, 1993)". The mixture consisting of chemicals and slurry produced the highest yield, but the best quality and best health of the plants were achieved after using pure slurry (Jianmin *et al.*, 1992). In another study, Maskey (1978) reported that a combination of 50% dry slurry + 50% chemical fertilizer gave the highest wheat yield compare to bio-slurry and chemical fertilizer alone.

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